

Studies in Quinones. Part I. Azophenols: Monophenylhydrazones of Quinones

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Phenylhydrazines on condensation with quinones give rise to products which behave both as azophenols and as monophenylhydrazones of quinones. Such derivatives from six quinones and nine substituted phenylhydrazines have been prepared and characterised.

Following the observations (Zincke and Bindewald, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 3026) that 1,4-naphthaquinone when condensed with phenylhydrazine gave rise to a product which behaved both as a 1,4-naphthaquinone monophenylhydrazone and as phenylazonaphthol, the reaction was further investigated by a number of workers (Borsch, *Annalen*, 1904, 334, 143; 1905, 340, 85; 1905, 343, 176; 1907, 357; 171; *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 669, 1287; *Annalen* 1926, 450, 75; Giacolone, *Gazzetta*, 1928, 58, 409; Mazzara, *ibid.*, 1879, 9, 424, Kuhn & Bar, *Annalen*, 1935, 518, 143).

The present work has been undertaken with a view to studying the compounds obtained by condensation of simple quinones, viz., *p*-benzoquinone, thymoquinone, *p*-toluquinone, chloranil, anthraquinone and β -methylantraquinone with several substituted phenylhydrazines, viz., 4-nitro-(I), 2-bromo-4-nitro-(II), 2-chloro-4-nitro-(III), 4-chloro-2-nitro-(IV), 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-(V), 2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-(VI), 4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-(VII), 6-bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-(VIII) and 6-chloro-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-(IX) phenylhydrazines.

The products so formed have been found identical with those obtained by condensing the diazonium salts of the corresponding anilines with phenols.

The behaviour of anthraquinone, β -methylantraquinone and chloranil has been found different from others. These fail to react with phenylhydrazines having substituents in both the *ortho* positions to the hydrazine group, but condense with the mono *ortho*-substituted ones. The products in the latter case also do not behave normally; neither these dissolve in alkali nor form acetyl derivatives or dihydrazones (with phenylhydrazine). Azophenols from other quinones dissolve in aqueous sodium hydroxide, can be acetylated, yield dihydrazones with phenylhydrazine and give coloured solutions with concentrated sulphuric acid.

The azophenols are all coloured, varying from deep red to dark chocolate in shade, slightly soluble in alcohol and more easily in acetic acid from which they can be crystallised.

EXPERIMENTAL

Azophenols

Condensation of Nitrophenylhydrazines with quinones.—An ethanolic solution of a nitrophenylhydrazine and a quinone in equimolecular proportions was heated in presence of a small amount of HCl (conc.). On cooling (and in some cases on adding a little water) the azophenol derivative separated. It was crystallised from acetic acid.

TABLE IA

Azophenols from p-benzoquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

No.	Phenyl-hydrazine	Azophenol (1'-azo-4'-ol)	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	I	4-Nitro-	211°	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ N ₃	N : 17.42%	17.28
2.	II	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	186°	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃ Br	Br : 24.53	24.84
3.	III	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	106°	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 13.03	12.79
4.	IV	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	178°	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 12.48	12.70
5.	V	2-Chloro-4, 6-dinitro	180°	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 10.76	11.00
6.	VI	2-Bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	183°	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 21.93	21.79
7.	VII	4,6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	225°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₄	N : 18.42	18.54
8.	VIII	6-Bromo-2, 4-dinitro-3-methyl-	198°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 21.21	20.99
9.	IX	6-Chloro-2, 4-dinitro-3-methyl-	200°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 10.81	10.54

TABLE IIA

Azophenols from thymoquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

No.	Phenyl-hydrazine	Azothymol (1'-azo-2'-methyl-5'-isopropyl-4'-ol.)	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	I	4-Nitro-	168°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	N : 14.31%	14.04
2.	II	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	176°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Br	Br : 21.33	21.16
3.	III	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	185°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.92	10.64
4.	IV	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	150°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.28	10.64
5.	V	2-Chloro-4, 6-dinitro-	193°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.69	9.37
6.	VI	2-Bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	185°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 18.68	18.91
7.	VII	4,6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	205°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₄	N : 15.39	15.64
8.	VIII	6-Bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	196°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 18.47	18.30
9.	IX	6-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	202°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.62	9.04

TABLE IIIA

Azophenols from p-toluquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

No.	Phenyl-hydrazine	Azocresol (1'-azo-3'-methyl-4'-ol).	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	I	4-Nitro-	203°	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃	N : 16.57%	16.34
2.	II	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	161°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	Br : 23.83	23.65
3.	III	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	176°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 12.22	12.17
4.	IV	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	128°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 12.49	12.17
5.	V	2-Chloro-4, 6-dinitro-	160°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 10.91	10.54
6.	VI	2-Bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	156°	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 21.24	20.99
7.	VII	4,6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	157°	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₄	N : 17.93	17.72
8.	VIII	6-Bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	152°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 20.58	20.25
9.	IX	6-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	150°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 10.49	10.13

Condensation of Nitrobenzenediazonium chlorides with phenols—(a). A nitroaniline, dissolved in 2½ times its molecular proportions of HCl (conc.) was diazotised. The filtered diazonium chloride solution was added to the requisite quantity of a phenol, dissolved in methanol, treated with an excess of aqueous sodium acetate solution, and well stirred. The product separating was crystallised from acetic acid.

(b) Sodium nitrite (0.11) was added slowly with vigorous stirring to H_2SO_4 (conc., 40 c.c.), cooled in an ice bath. After addition of the nitrite the mixture was warmed to about 40-45° till a clear solution was obtained. It was then cooled and a dinitroaniline (0.1 M.) was added in small portions with stirring. After keeping at 10-15° for 4 hours, the diazotised amine was added to about one litre of ice-cold water and the solution was filtered. The clear solution obtained was added slowly with stirring to a solution of a phenol (0.1 M.) in acetic acid (300 c.c.) containing sodium acetate (150 g.). During the first part of addition the temperature was kept at 10-15°, but after about 100 c.c. of the diazonium salt solution had been added, the temperature was lowered to 5°. After all of the diazonium solution had been added, the reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour, filtered, and washed thoroughly with cold water. The product was crystallised from acetic acid.

A mixture of the azo compounds from the above two methods showed no depression in m.p.

Acetylation of Azophenols—A mixture of azophenol with three times its weight of acetic anhydride and some anhydrous sodium acetate was boiled for half an hour. The acetyl derivative formed was crystallised from acetic acid.

Phenylhydrazones of Azophenols—An alcoholic solution of an azophenol and phenylhydrazine in equimolecular proportions was heated on water bath for an hour. The product was crystallised from alcohol.

Analytical data and characteristics of azophenols obtained from different phenylhydrazines and quinones together with those of their acetyl and phenylhydrazine derivatives are given in Tables I to VI

TABLE IV

Monophenylhydrazones from chloranil and substituted phenylhydrazines.

Monophenylhydrazone formed					
S.No.	Phenylhydrazine.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	4-Nitro-	300°	$C_{12}H_5O_3N_3Cl_4$	Cl : 37.68%	37.27%
2.	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	300°	$C_{12}H_4O_3N_3Cl_4Br$	N : 9.01	9.13
3.	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	"	$C_{12}H_4O_3N_3Cl_5$	Cl : 42.91	42.72
4.	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	290°	$C_{12}H_4O_3N_3Cl_5$	Cl : 42.41	42.72
5.	4,6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	300°	$C_{13}H_6O_3N_3Cl_4$	Cl : 32.68	32.27

TABLE V

Monophenylhydrazones from anthraquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

Monophenylhydrazone formed.					
S.No.	Phenylhydrazines	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	4-Nitro-	300°	$C_{20}H_{13}O_3N_3$	N : 12.58%	12.24%
2.	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	"	$C_{20}H_{12}O_3N_3Br$	Br : 18.62	18.95
3.	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	"	$C_{20}H_{12}O_3N_3Cl$	Cl : 9.71	9.40
4.	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	"	$C_{20}H_{12}O_3N_3Cl$	Cl : 9.63	9.40
5.	4:6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	"	$C_{21}H_{14}O_3N_4$	N : 13.61	13.93

TABLE IB

No.	M.P.	Colour	Acetyl derivatives.		Calc.	M.P.	Colour.	Phenylhydrazones.		Calc.
			Formula.	Found.				Formula.	Found.	
1.	147°	Light orange	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	N : 14.61%	14.73%	232°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₅	N : 20.96%	21.02%
2.	158°	Light brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃ Br	Br : 21.89	21.98	216°	Orange-red	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₅ Br	Br : 19.23	19.41
3.	163°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 11.25	11.11	225°	Dull red	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 9.78	9.65
4.	160°	Do	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 11.31	11.11	212°	Brown	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 9.81	9.65
5.	166°	Light orange	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.63	9.74	228°	Brown-red	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 8.44	8.61
6.	158°	Orange yellow	C ₁₄ H ₈ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 19.71	19.56	226°	Do	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 17.71	17.51
7.	187°	Do	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₄ Br	N : 16.39	16.28	245°	Chocolate	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₆	N : 21.26	21.43
8.	165°	Orange	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 19.08	18.91	241°	Dull red	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 17.11	16.98
9.	170°	Light orange	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.33	9.38	224°	Orange-red	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 8.17	8.32

The number of azophenols corresponds to those listed in Table IA.

TABLE IIB

No.	M.P.	Colour	Acetyl derivatives.		Calc.	M.P.	Colour	Phenylhydrazones		Calc.
			Formula.	Found.				Formula.	Found.	
1.	145°	Reddish yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	N : 12.09%	12.31%	218°	Dirty yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₅	N : 18.10%	17.99%
2.	143°	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Br	Br : 19.31	19.04	208°	Brown-red	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₅ Br	Br : 16.83	17.09
3.	144°	Brick-red	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.57	9.45	230°	Orange-red	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 8.54	8.38
4.	115°	Red	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.34	9.45	202°	Reddish brown	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 8.66	9.38
5.	125°	Scarlet-red	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.63	8.44	245°(d)	Brown-red	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 7.41	7.57
6.	128°	Brown-red	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 17.38	17.20	235°	Red	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 15.38	15.59
7.	139°	Reddish yellow	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄	N : 13.76	14.00	250°(d)	Do	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆	N : 18.92	18.75
8.	145°	Red	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 16.86	16.70	248°	Dirty red	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 15.31	15.18
9.	152°	Do	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.35	8.17	256°	Do	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 7.19	7.35

The number of azophenols corresponds to those listed in Table IIA

TABLE IIIB

No.	M.P.	Colour	Acetyl derivatives.		Calc.	M.P.	Colour.	Phenylhydrazones.		Calc.
			Formula.	Found.				Formula.	Found.	
1.	145°	Yellowish brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	N : 14.25%	14.05%	225°	Yellowish brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₅	N : 19.98%	20.17%
2.	145°	Do	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Br	Br : 21.28	21.10	205°	Orange	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₅ Br	Br : 16.51	18.76
3.	145°	Light brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.89	10.04	212°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 9.43	9.29
4.	120°	Yellowish brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.84	10.64	198°	Orange-red	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₅ Cl	Cl : 9.39	9.29
5.	140°	Orange-red	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.15	9.38	199°	Yellowish red	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 8.11	8.32
6.	142°	Do	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 16.67	18.01	202°	Light brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ Br	Br : 17.13	16.98
7.	143°	Yellowish red	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₄	N : 15.43	15.64	216°	Dull red	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆	N : 20.72	20.69
8.	138°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 18.18	18.31	220°	Do	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 16.65	16.49
9.	140°	* Do	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.21	9.04	210°	Yellowish red	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 8.32	8.06

The number of azophenols corresponds to those listed in Table IIIA

TABLE VI

Monophenylhydrazones from β -methylanthraquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

S.No.	Phenylhydrazines.	Monophenylhydrazone formed.			
		M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	4-Nitro-	174°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃	N : 11.48%	11.76%
2.	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	178°	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Br	Br : 18.77	18.34
3.	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	172°	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 8.84	9.06
4.	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	166°	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.34	9.06
5.	4:6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	142°	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	N : 13.03	13.46

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